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Research Article

**SLEEP QUALITY AND MIGRAINE OUTCOME IN
THE POPULATION IN THE WESTERN REGION IN SAUDI
ARABIA****Naif Edah Alomairi¹, Ohud Ali Alghamdi², Elaf Mohammed Althobaiti³,
Shatha Kamal Alhalabi⁴, Dalal Ali Alghamdi⁵, Hamoud Ali Albdali⁶**¹- Department of internal medicine, college of medicine, Taif university, Taif 21944, Saudi Arabia.^{2,3,4,5,6} - Medical students, college of medicine, Taif university, Taif 21944, Saudi Arabia.**Abstract:**

Migraine and sleep disorders are prevalent chronic disorders that can be burdensome cases. They are common in the general population and can have significant socioeconomic impacts. It has not been decided so far if sleep quality affects migraine prevalence.

***Aim:** The objective of this study is to assess the relationship between sleep quality and migraine among the population in the western region of Saudi Arabia.*

***Methods:** a cross-sectional study was conducted among an adult population of 414 participants in the western region of Saudi Arabia from March to May 2023. The data collection tools were the ID MigraineTM screener and the Athens Insomnia Scale (AIS). Data analysis was conducted using the Chi-squared test (χ^2).*

***Results:** 414 participants participated in the study; most of them had a headache (76.3%), with nearly two-thirds having migraine disorders (68.7%). Poor sleep quality was determined among more than half of the participants (59.2%). There was a significant association between migraine prevalence and sleep quality; poor sleep quality rate was higher among cases with migraine compared to others (67.7% vs. 54.5%) (p-value=0.024).*

***Conclusion:** It was concluded migraine largely affected the participants' sleep quality. The study underscores the importance of considering sleep quality as an integral part of migraine management and highlights the need for future studies that use objective measures to assess sleep quality.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Migraine is the most prevalent type of headache illness (Chu et al., 2021). According to the WHO, migraine is the second-most incapacitating neurological ailment and the third-most common medical condition worldwide (Duan et al., 2022). It is characterized by strong, lateralized, throbbing, or pulsatile head sensations (Lin et al., 2016).

Associated symptoms of migraine attacks include nausea, vomiting, sound sensitivity, and light sensitivity (Lin et al., 2016). Certain studies have revealed a connection between migraine and sleep issues, sleeping patterns and migraine frequency, however, are still unknown (Lin et al., 2016).

Sleep is one of the most significant physiological processes, The endocrine and immunological systems, as well as cognitive, emotional, and memory functions, are all supported by sleep. Sleep and migraine have mutually complex effects as an alteration in sleep may result in migraine and lead to a change in its symptoms and treatment.(Saçmacı et al., 2022).

Different studies revealed that individuals with migraine experienced poorer sleep quality than those who were free of the disease.

A study carried out recently indicated that insomnia patients were more likely to become migraineurs than those experiencing no insomnia (Chu et al., 2021). Similarly, the percentage of prevalence of poor sleep quality in migraineurs is higher compared to that in those having no migraine (Duan et al., 2022). Poor sleep quality in the Taiwanese population was associated with high migraine frequency, and poor sleepers suffered a higher prevalence. These interrelations happen in migraine with aura and without aura (Lin et al., 2016).

Poor sleep quality was high among university students with migraine compared to that among Chinese students (Zhao et al., 2022).

In contrast, many studies revealed the non-existence of a link between poor sleep quality and migraine (Fox and Davis 1998; Bruni et al., 2004)

The ID MigraineTM is a widely used migraine screening tool that has demonstrated good validity for migraineurs' diagnosis at primary health care services, as it investigates the major aspects of migraine headache, which are nausea, photophobia,

and disability (Lipton et al., 2003). Lipton et al. created and validated this tool, which can be quickly applied to large populations (Lipton et al., 2003). Tfelt-Hansen et al. (2012) estimated the sensitivity, specificity, and positive predictive value of this test in primary care to be 81%, 75%, and 93%, respectively. This test has also been validated for use with adolescent students, with a sensitivity of 62.1% and a specificity of 71.1% (Lipton et al., 2003; Tfelt-Hansen et al., 2012). It was also used in research on university students in Arab countries and Saudi Arabia (Alwahbi et al., 2017; Garah et al., 2016).

The Athens Insomnia Scale (AIS) was used to assess sleep quality. Respondents used a Likert-type scale to indicate how severely certain sleep difficulties affected them in the previous month. Scores range from 0 (indicating that the item in question has not been a problem) to 3 (indicating more severe sleep problems). To correctly distinguish between insomnia patients and controls, a cutoff score of 6 was used (Soldato et al., 2003).

In a study carried out in Saudi Arabia, 5.17% of young females (17- to 26- years old) suffered from migraine with no correlation detected between poor sleep quality migraine, whereas high-stress scores were significantly correlated with migraine in adult females (Rafique et al., 2020).

A limited number of studies were conducted in Saudi Arabia, especially in the western region. Thus, the objective of this study is to assess to what extent sleep quality affects having migraine among the population in the western region of Saudi Arabia.

Subjects and methods

Ethical considerations: Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the research ethics committee of Taif University, Saudi Arabia. Application NO.:44-322, date:2023-05-07.

Study design: A cross-sectional study was carried out in the Western region, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, from March to May 2023.

Sampling and population: The inclusion criteria were residents in the Western region of Saudi Arabia with an age above 18 years. However, the exclusion criteria were residents younger than 18 years and residents of other regions of Saudi Arabia.

Data collection: a pre-designed online questionnaire was used to collect data about the participants'

demographic data and smoking status. A stepwise approach was carried out to assess the prevalence of headaches, it contained three sections the first question aimed to screen the presence of headaches among participants, this is followed by a set of questions :

Did you have two or more headaches in the last three months?, Have you felt sick or sick in your stomach as a result of your headaches in the last three months? , Did light bother you when you had a headache (much more than when you didn't)? Did your headache interfere with your ability to work, study, or do your job for at least one day?

A migraine headache test diagnosis requires at least two positive responses (Lipton et al., 2003).

Data analysis: Data were analyzed using (SPSS) version 26. To test the relationship between variables, qualitative data was expressed as numbers and percentages, and the Chi-squared test (χ^2) was

used. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Total 414 subjects participated in the study, with an age of more than 18 years (table 1). The majority of the participants, 316 (76.3%), had reported headaches, with 217 (68.7%) having migraine (Figure 1).

Based on the Athens Insomnia Scale (AIS) score classification, 59.2% of the participants had poor sleep quality (Figure 2).

The study observed the non-existence of a link between migraine prevalence and sleep quality and participants' demographics or smoking status ($p > 0.05$). (Tables 2-3).

On the other hand, the prevalence of migraine was significantly higher among participants who had poor sleep quality ($p = 0.05$). (Table 4 and Figure 3).

Table 1. Distribution of studied participants according to their demographic data and smoking status (No.: 414)

Variable	No. (%)
Age (years)	
20-24	113 (27.3)
25-30	47 (11.4)
31-35	41 (9.9)
36-40	46 (11.1)
>40	167 (40.3)
Nationality	
Saudi	378 (91.3)
None Saudi	36 (8.9)
Marital status	
Unmarried	152 (36.7)
Married	262 (63.3)
Educational level	
Primary	4 (1)
Middle	10 (2.4)
Secondary	91 (22)
University and above	309 (74.6)
Employment	
Employed	156 (37.7)
Student	99 (23.9)
Unemployed	159 (38.4)
Smoking status	
Non-smoker	377 (91.1)
Smoker	37 (8.9)

Figure 1. The prevalence of headache and migraine among tested subjects.

Figure 2. The sleep quality among the respondents .

Table 2. Relationship between migraine prevalence and participants' demographics and smoking statue (No.: 316)

Variable	Migraine		χ^2	p-value
	Yes No. (%)	No No. (%)		
Age (years)			4.34	0.362
20-24	61 (28.1)	31 (31.3)		
25-30	26 (12)	7 (7.1)		
31-35	27 (12.4)	7 (7.1)		
36-40	24 (11.1)	12 (12.1)		
>40	79 (36.4)	42 (42.2)		
Nationality			0.001	0.989
Saudi	193 (88.9)	88 (88.9)		
Non-Saudi	24 (11.1)	11 (11.1)		
Marital status			1.1	0.293
Unmarried	88 (40.6)	34 (34.3)		
Married	129 (59.4)	65 (65.7)		
Educational level			1.18	0.757
Primary	2 (0.9)	1 (1)		
Middle	4 (1.8)	3 (3)		
Secondary	54 (24.9)	20 (20.2)		
University and above	157 (72.4)	75 (75.8)		
Employment			1.61	0.446
Employed	88 (40.6)	33 (33.3)		
Student	54 (24.9)	26 (26.3)		
Unemployed	75 (34.6)	40 (40.4)		
Smoking status			0.001	0.971
Non-smoker	197 (90.8)	90 (90.9)		
Smoker	20 (9.2)	9 (9.1)		

Table 3. Relationship between migraine prevalence and participants' demographics and smoking status (No.: 414)

Variable	Sleep Quality		χ^2	p-value
	Good No. (%)	Poor No. (%)		
Age (years)			4.14	0.387
20-24	38 (22.5)	75 (30.6)		
25-30	22 (13)	25 (10.2)		
31-35	17 (10.1)	24 (9.8)		
36-40	22 (13)	24 (9.8)		
>40	70 (41.4)	97 (38.6)		
Nationality			0.91	0.339
Saudi	157 (92.9)	221 (90.2)		
Non- Saudi	12 (7.1)	24 (9.8)		
Marital status			2.78	0.095
Unmarried	54 (32)	98 (40)		
Married	115 (68)	147 (60)		
Educational level			1.01	0.797
Primary	1 (0.6)	3 (1.2)		
Middle	5 (3)	5 (2)		
Secondary	35 (20.7)	56 (22.9)		
University and above	128 (75.7)	181 (73.9)		
Employment			0.5	0.777
Employed	63 (37.3)	93 (38)		
Student	38 (22.5)	61 (24.9)		
Unemployed	68 (40.2)	91 (37.1)		
Smoking status			0.54	0.461
Non-smoker	156 (92.3)	221 (90.2)		
Smoker	13 (7.7)	24 (9.8)		

Table 4. Relationship between migraine prevalence and sleep quality (No.: 316)

Variable	Migraine		χ^2	p-value
	Yes No. (%)	No No. (%)		
Sleep Quality			5.11	0.024
Good sleep quality	70 (32.3)	45 (45.5)		
Poor sleep quality	147 (67.7)	54 (54.5)		

Figure 3. Relationship between migraine prevalence and sleep quality (No.: 316)

N.B.: ($\chi^2 = 5.11$, p-value = **0.024**)

DISCUSSION:

Migraine is one of the most occasional kinds of headache disorders associated with severe, pulsing, or throbbing sensations that typically affect one side of the head. Migraine sufferers often experience a poor quality of life and disability due to their condition. Moreover, it has been observed that individuals with migraine frequently have comorbid psychiatric conditions like anxiety and depression. Additionally, the literature suggested an association between migraine and sleep disorders (Lin et al., 2016).

Thus, the purpose of this study is to check whether there is association between sleep quality and migraine among adult population of 414 participants in the western region of Saudi Arabia.

According to the ID Migraine™, it was found that most of our participants had headaches (76.3%), with nearly two-thirds having migraine disorders (68.7%). Migraine prevalence among our subjects was similar to other Saudi studies, which reported a migraine prevalence of 68.4% among Taif University students and 61.8% among Taibah University students (Desoukyet al., 2019) (Al- Al-Jabry et al., 2015). On the other side, a previous Saudi study found a higher prevalence of intense headaches among their participants (98%) (Rafique et al., 2020). However, the prevalence of migraine was less than in our study (5.17%) Other studies conducted in Jazan, Iran, and Athens reported a lower prevalence of migraine among their cases

was 5.0% and 7.4%, 2.4%, respectively (Shabi et al., 2020) (Shahraka et al., 2011) (Mitsikostas et al., 1996). These differences can be associated with variations in study designs, methodology, and types of data collection tools that were used. Other factors might include different racial, climatic, environmental factors, socioeconomic status, or nutritional habits.

This study considered age, nationality, marital status, educational level, and smoking status variables and their association with migraine incidences and sleep quality. There was no significant association between the different variables and the incidence of migraine or sleep quality among participants. A prior study's results were different from our findings and indicated significant interactions between poor sleep quality and the risk of migraine regarding gender, age, and education level (p -value <0.05) (Duan et al., 2020). Moreover, it was mentioned that smoking, alcohol, and coffee may be triggers of migraine attacks (Lin et al., 2016). However, in the present study, there was no observed relation between the participants' smoking status and migraine prevalence. Prior studies were contradictory to our results and found that smokers, alcohol, and coffee drinkers had higher migraine prevalence compared to others (Lin et al., 2016) (Erusalimschy & Moreira Filho, 2002). Sleep is a crucial physiological process and individuals' deprivation that accounts for up to one-third of human life. It is widely regarded as one of the most critical psychophysiological processes for brain function and mental health (Regier et al., 2012). Interestingly, in our study, poor sleep quality was determined among more than half of the study subjects (59.2%). In addition, it was estimated that individuals with migraines had a 2-fold higher risk (OR, 1.7) of developing insomnia than subjects without (Ødegård et al., 2013). On the other hand, in the present study, there was a significant association between migraine prevalence and sleep quality; poor sleep quality rate was higher among cases with migraine compared to others (67.7% vs. 54.5%) (p -value=0.024). Similarly, several studies documented a significantly higher prevalence of insomnia and insomnia complaints among patients with migraine compared to those without headaches (Kim et al., 2018) (Lovati et al., 2010) (Yeung et al., 2010). Additionally, a higher prevalence of migraine has been indicated in individuals with insomnia compared to those without (Kim et al., 2018). Furthermore, previous data supported our results and reported a positive correlation between poor sleep quality and migraine (Parashar et al., 2014) (Seidel et al., 2009) (Alberti, 2006) (Sahota, 2003). Kim et al. and Gori et al. documented that poor sleep quality was

considerably higher in migraine subjects compared to controls (Kim et al., 2017) (Gori et al., 2005). This correlation may be due to the ability of sleep disorders to trigger hyperalgesic responses in the central nervous system (CNS) by increasing the nociceptor excitability, which leads to central sensitization (Rains et al., 2015). In contrast, a study conducted in Saudi Arabia revealed that there was no significant difference between the migraineurs and controlling principles regarding sleep quality and different sleep parameters (Rafique et al., 2020). Another study also showed no exact association between migraine headaches and disturbed sleep (Fox & Davis, 1998). However, this study has two important limitations that should be taken into account. First, we used a cross-sectional design, which may restrict the causal inference between migraine and sleep quality. Second, subjective sleep quality was examined with the self-rated scoring system; we did not evaluate sleep with an objective assessment.

CONCLUSION:

This study provides valuable insight into the relationship between sleep quality and migraine in the Saudi Arabian population. The result indicated that it was found that most of our participants had headaches, with two-thirds having migraine disorders. In addition, poor sleep quality was found among more than half of our participants. There was a significant relationship between migraine and the participants' sleep quality. It underscores the importance of considering sleep quality as an integral part of migraine management and highlights the need for future studies that use objective measures to assess sleep quality. Generally, this study emphasizes the need for healthcare professionals to consider sleep quality when evaluating and treating migraine patients to improve the quality of their lives and reduce disability.

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